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Title :Enhancing Bayombong Daycare Teacher’s Pedagogical Skills: Bridging Implications for a Relevant Extension Program

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Abstract

This study determined the number of child development workers/teachers in the Day Care Centers of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, who needed pedagogical support across the Standards Competency of Child Development Workers. It identified specific areas where these educators require further support or training to effectively deliver quality and relevant childcare services. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, the research combined a survey and an interview to gather data from a total of **eighteen** child development workers in **Bayombong** day care centers.

Findings reveal that while many workers demonstrate baseline competence in core areas of early childhood development, there are critical gaps in understanding developmental characteristics, implementing health and safety protocols, and identifying children at risk for developmental delays. Moreover, opportunities for professional development, such as seminars and training, were found to be limited and infrequent.

These gaps underscore the urgent need for sustained, high-quality professional development programs tailored to the evolving needs of early childhood educators. The results of this study contribute to broader discussions on improving the quality of early childhood education in community-based settings and may serve as a basis for future policy-making, curriculum development, and targeted training initiatives.

Keywords: child development, developmental characteristics, professional development

Introduction

In 1999, the Philippine Government launched a five-year Early Child Development (ECD) project to attain the country’s human development goals to reduce poverty, as an instrument to meet the government’s commitment to the International Convention on the Rights of Children. In 2002, the government institutionalized the program by legislating the Early Child Care and Development (ECCD) Act, which established governance structures and delivery systems for children aged 0-6 years. It created the Council for the Welfare of Children (CWC) as the highest policymaking body for children’s concerns. The program uses health, **early education**, and social services programs that provide for the basic needs of young children. The program is an interdepartmental partnership of many national agencies.

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The program recognized the need for full partnership with the local government units (LGUs) and also nongovernmental organizations. The ECCD Act (RA 8980) ensures that Filipino children receive care and development during the most crucial stage of their growth. By 20230. The ECCD Council shall have fully implemented a comprehensive, integrative, and sustainable National System for Early Childhood Care and Development throughout the country. One of its mandates is to develop a national system for the recruitment, registration, accreditation, **continuing education** and equivalency, and credential system of ECCD service providers, supervisors, and administrators to improve and professionalize the ECCD sector and upgrade quality standards of public and private ECCD programs.

Starting education at the right age is a head start in learning and predicts higher success in school. Data suggest that children who received Early Childhood Education (ECE) are more likely to attend primary education at the age of 6, which is the official primary school starting age in the Philippines, compared to those who did not attend ECE. An ECD specialist says “Children have the right to quality pre-primary education, which is the foundation of a child’s journey. Every stage of education that follows relies on its success. If we fail to provide quality early childhood education, we limit the prospects of individual children, as well as the country’s human capital needed to reduce inequalities and promote peaceful, prosperous societies.” Considering the crucial role of Child Development Workers (CDWs) play in facilitating a smooth transition from early learning and development to formal education, the need to prepare them is a must.

Research tells that early childhood education teachers in the Philippines face several challenges. These include the lack of educational facilities, a lack of structured curriculum, inadequate funding, and **issues with teacher’s training and qualifications**. The COVID-19 pandemic has further exacerbated the challenges, with teachers experiencing difficulties in time management, **pedagogical demands**, economic and financial demands, and learning environment demands (2023-International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development). Reports also stated that since most of the ECD leaders, particularly the ECD focal persons, are often selected by the political authorities at the local level, they may not have ECD and teaching experience. Additionally, they may have little knowledge of supervising child development teachers/workers (Save the Children 2021 Study). For many years, ECD leaders have raised concerns about the lack of appropriate preservice professional training and continuing education opportunities for CDT/Ws. This usually resulted in most CDTs being unaware of developmentally appropriate, gender-sensitive, and inclusive practices (Save the Children Philippines 2019). In addition, there was also limited training for ECD leaders to develop professional capabilities and personal qualities needed to support an already strained workforce. Teachers are the most important factors in affecting change in learners’ lives and well-being. In the call of duty, they make important decisions to realize this lifetime vocation. The totality of their actions as teachers comprises their instructional practices. McGregor (2007) analyzes the essential practices of high-quality teaching and learning and concludes that: “if we are to improve schools, as measured by improved student performance, we must craft improvement strategies that directly impact what happens in the teaching and learning environment.” According to him, effective teachers are teachers who (1) make maximum use of instructional time, (2) present

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materials in a way to meet students' needs, (3) monitor progress, and (4) plan opportunities for students to apply learning. For these to be mastered by teachers, Bilbao (2013) contends that they must have the following skills: literacy, numeracy, information and communication technology competence, ethical behavior, personal and social competence, and intellectual understanding.

Empowering and enhancing the capacity of CDWs is one aspect of improving early childhood education in the Philippines. If teachers lack the competency because of their qualification or lack of training, this will be counterproductive because the most affected are the children, as it compromises the quality of learning. There is a need to professionalize child development workers and align the various competencies of Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD) workers with the educational programs in schools (2023- EDCOM 2). This is the conclusion by the Commissioners of the Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM 2) during a hearing between the Commission and the ECCD Council. According to data from the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), only 52.2% of child development workers (CDWs) in the Philippines are college graduates, with the rest of CDWs having a high school diploma (16.8%), vocational certificate (6.1%), some college units (24.8%), and post-graduate degrees (0.2%). The Commission also noted that about 52.6% of CDWs are aged 46 years old and above. By improving the capabilities of daycare workers, there is an assurance that every Filipino child is equipped with appropriate skills to build his future in time. Quality Education is an enabler of development and crucial to help people overcome poverty.

Saint Mary's University Grade School, as a partner of the Day Care Centers in Bayombong, with its passion for Christ's Mission aims to collaborate with the LGU in the continuous training of the Child Development Workers. Through this research, the Pedagogical Competencies of the Child Development Workers of Bayombong, the results will lead to efforts to be made in providing comprehensive development opportunities necessary to advance the skills and attitudes of the CDWs of Bayombong: establishing mentorship programs and support networks for the CDWs and continuous learning opportunities that will empower them to provide high quality and developmentally appropriate instruction that will eventually support the accreditation of all the Day Care centers of Bayombong under the supervision/management of the Department of Social Welfare and Development.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

Core Competencies for Early Childhood Educators

Child development workers (CDWs) play a pivotal role in fostering the growth and well-being of children, particularly in early childhood settings. A comprehensive understanding of the competencies required for effective practice is essential for enhancing the quality of care and education provided.

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Research has identified several key competencies that are fundamental for early childhood educators:

- 1. Child Development Knowledge:** A deep understanding of child development theories and practices is crucial. This knowledge enables educators to create developmentally appropriate learning experiences that cater to the individual needs of each child.
- 2. Effective Communication Skills:** Strong communication abilities are essential for building positive relationships with children, parents, and colleagues. Clear and empathetic communication fosters a supportive learning environment and facilitates collaboration among all stakeholders.
- 3. Classroom Management and Pedagogical Skills:** Competence in managing classroom dynamics and implementing effective teaching strategies is vital. Training programs have demonstrated that enhancing these skills can lead to improved teaching outcomes and increased job satisfaction among CDWs .
- 4. Cultural Competence and Inclusivity:** Educators must be adept at recognizing and respecting cultural diversity. This includes understanding the unique backgrounds of children and families and integrating inclusive practices into the curriculum and daily interactions.
- 5. Family and Community Engagement:** Building strong partnerships with families and communities supports children's development and learning. Educators should be skilled in engaging families in the educational process and fostering a collaborative approach to child development.
- 6. Health, Safety, and Nutrition:** Ensuring the physical well-being of children is a fundamental responsibility. Educators should be knowledgeable about health and safety practices and promote healthy habits and nutrition among children.

Competency Frameworks and Professional Development

Various competency frameworks have been developed to guide the professional development of CDWs:

ZERO TO THREE Competencies: This framework outlines competencies for professionals working with children from prenatal to age five, emphasizing the importance of understanding early childhood development and fostering supportive relationships.

California Early Childhood Educator Competencies: These competencies provide a comprehensive guide for educators, covering areas such as child development, cultural diversity, family engagement, and health and safety.

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Competency Standards for Child Development Workers. The ECCD Council developed competency standards for child development workers. This consists of seven domains: (1) Child Growth, development and learning, (2) Health, nutrition, safety, and well-being, (3) Curriculum, (4) Learning environment and experiences, (5) Assessment and reporting, (6) family involvement and community linkages, and (7) Personal and Professional Development. This specifies seventy-five competencies.

Implications for Practice and Policy

The development and implementation of competency frameworks are critical for enhancing the effectiveness of CDWs. These frameworks provide a structured approach to professional development, ensuring that educators possess the necessary skills and knowledge to support children's growth. Additionally, ongoing training and support are essential to address the evolving needs of children and families and to adapt to emerging challenges in the field of early childhood education.

A well-defined set of competencies is fundamental for the professional growth of child development workers and the quality of care and education provided to young children. By focusing on these competencies, educators can better support children's development and contribute to positive outcomes for families and communities.

Philippine Initiatives on Early Childhood Education

1. The Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM 2) emphasizes the need for structured training programs to professionalize CDWs. It advocates for aligning competencies with educational programs to enhance the effectiveness of early childhood education. The Commission necessitates the upskilling and training opportunities to professionalize child development workers (EDCOM 2, 2023).

According to data from the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), only 52.2% of child development workers (CDWs) in the Philippines are college graduates, with the rest of CDWs having a high school diploma (16.8%), vocational certificate (6.1%), some college units (24.8%), and post-graduate degrees (0.2%). The Commission also noted that about 52.6% of CDWs are aged 46 years old and above.

During the hearing, Senate Basic Education Committee Chair and EDCOM 2 Co-Chair Senator Sherwin Gatchalian urged the ECCD Council to explore a “Philippine-style” of early childhood education that is aligned with international standards. The EDCOM urged the ECCD Council to explore two pathways that child development workers (CDWs) can take for career advancement. Firstly, by certification through the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), and secondly, for the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) to create a ladderized program for CDWs.

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Senate Bill 2029, filed in March 2023 by Gatchalian aims to address issues with the qualifications and career progression of preschool teachers and workers. The bill provides for the professionalization of child development workers and teachers, and seeks to streamline the delivery of ECCD services.

Consequently, the Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM II) lauds the signing of the Joint Circular (JC) between the Department of Budget and Management (DBM) and the Department of Education (DepEd) to establish Child Development Centers (CDCs) in low-income local government units (LGUs). The ceremonial signing, witnessed by His Excellency President Ferdinand R. Marcos, Jr., marks a significant step toward addressing gaps in early childhood care and development (ECCD) identified in the EDCOM II Year 2 Report, "Fixing the Foundations."

2 . Implemented by UNICEF Philippines in collaboration with the University of the Philippines Center for Women's Studies Foundation and Northwest Samar State University, a project on Development and Learning Loss Recovery: Strengthening Systems for capacity Building of CDWs and CDTs was launched. This project provided training to over 100 CDWs and CDTs. The program focused on addressing learning loss and enhancing the capacity of educators to support early childhood development effectively.

3. The Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) is set to launch a new certification program targeting CDWs with only high school diplomas. This initiative aims to upskill approximately 2,854 CDWs, thereby improving the quality of early childhood education across the country.

An Impact study (2024) evaluated the extension project on Empowering Child Development Workers in Classroom Management and Pedagogy. A training program in Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, aimed to enhance the teaching competencies of CDWs. The results indicated significant improvements in classroom management, pedagogy, and overall teaching effectiveness, leading to a more nurturing learning environment for young children. Likewise, local Philippine studies have been done on the professionalization, training, and supervision of CDWs/CDTs (Floresca, Nunez, and Cristobal et al, 2017, Umali and Velasco, 2025, Asian Development Bank, 2012). These studies reveal the educational backgrounds, government eligibilities, and ECCD related trainings. Due to financial constraints of local government units, hiring qualified CDWs/CDTs, and training for capacity-building has been limited.

Theoretical Framework

Early Childhood Education involves integrating concepts and thoughts from diverse fields such as education, psychology, and child development.

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Constructivism: Rooted in the idea that learners actively construct their own understanding and knowledge through experiences and reflection. Teachers can use instructional practices that facilitate active learning, problem-solving, and inquiry-based activities. They can create environments that encourage exploration and discovery, allowing children to construct meaning through hands-on experiences.

Developmental Learning: Piaget's stages of cognitive development and Vygotsky's sociocultural theory guide Teachers to alter their instructional practices to the developmental stage of the children they are teaching. They can scaffold learning experiences, providing suitable support and assistance based on each child's current level of development.

Social-Emotional Learning (SEL): Recognizing the importance of social and emotional development alongside cognitive development, Teachers can include SEL practices in their instruction. This involves nurturing skills such as self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and relationship-building through activities that encourage collaboration, communication, and conflict resolution.

Play-based learning: Recognizing play as a fundamental means of learning for young children, Child Teachers can integrate play-based instructional practices into their curriculum. They can craft learning experiences that promote creative play, adventure, and creativity, allowing children to develop cognitive, social, and emotional skills in meaningful settings.

Reflective Practice: Encouraging ongoing reflection and professional growth, Teachers can engage in thoughtful practices to assess the success of their instructional approaches and make informed modifications based on observations and comments. They can team up with colleagues, participate in professional development opportunities, and stay well-informed of current research and best practices in child development and education.

By grounding their instructional practices in these theoretical frameworks, Child Development teachers can create dynamic, responsive, and supportive learning environments that nurture the holistic development of every child.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

To get a total picture of the Child Development Workers, their profile was looked into vis-à-vis the Standard Competencies for Child Development Workers. Gaps/insights were drawn from their experiences. The results provided baseline data for the plan of action for the upskilling and continual improvement of the Child Development Workers.

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Statement of Objectives

The study aimed to determine the number of child development workers who needed pedagogical support/care. Specifically, it sought answers to the following objectives:

1. Determine the profile of the Child Development Workers (CDWs) of the Daycare Centers in Bayombong in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Number of years teaching daycare
 - 1.4 In-service training attended in daycare
2. Determine the number of child development workers who need pedagogical support and care on the following domains:
 - a. Child Growth and its Development,
 - b. Health, safety, and well-being,
 - c. Curriculum,
 - d. The Learning Environment and Experiences,
 - e. Assessment and Reporting,
 - f. Communicating and Partnering with Families and Community Linkages,
 - g. Personal and Professional Development.
3. Identify insights (gaps) from the experiences of the CDWs/Ts?
4. Propose a strategic plan of action that can address the gaps.

Methodology

A. Design

This study used qualitative and quantitative research approaches. Under the quantitative approach, the descriptive research design was employed to capture data accurately and appropriately. A survey questionnaire was used to determine the profile and the number of CDWs who needed pedagogical support and care across the ECCD Competency Standards. The qualitative approach included an interview that supplemented the data from the survey questionnaire

B. Locale

The study was conducted in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya in the following Daycare Centers: Bansing 1 Child Development Center (CDC), Bonfal East CDC, Bonfal Proper CDC, Bonfal West CDC, cabuaan CDC, Casat CDC, Don Domingo Maddela CDC, Don Mariano Marcos CDC, Don Mariano Perez CDC, Don Tomas Maddela CDC, La Torre North CDC,

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Luyang CDC Upper Magsayasay CDC, Magsaysay CDC, Masoc CDC, Salvacion CDC, Sta Rosa CDC, Vista Alegre CDC.

C. Participants and Sample

The respondents were the Child Development Teachers/Workers (CDT/Ws) of the Daycare Centers of Bayombong. A total of eighteen (18) Child Development Teachers/Workers agreed to be the respondents.

D. Instrument(s)

The tool that was used in gathering the data was a survey questionnaire on the Competency Standards for Child Development Teachers/Child Development Workers of the Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD) Council. The survey questionnaire is composed of seven (7) domains as follows: 1. Child Growth and Its development, 2. Health, safety and well-Being, 3. Curriculum, 4. The Learning Environment and Experiences, 5. Assessment and Reporting, 6. Communicating and Partnering with families and Community Linkages, 7. Personal and Professional development. Each of these standards is comprehensively described and has its corresponding standards and competencies. These competencies and standards were converted into tasks for easy administration. The tasks focus on what teachers/workers need to know and be able to do in all seven (7) domains to demonstrate that they are well-rounded and well-prepared to educate and care for young children. The domains and tasks are interrelated and together provide the complete picture of the “whole” professional teacher or worker. These competencies or tasks are written with the belief that all CDTs /CDWs and other childhood professionals develop skills over time on these tasks. As the teacher or worker becomes accomplished in one task, he/she develops professional goals and plans for skills in the next task level. The levels of competency establish a continuum from readiness skills of a beginner to skills necessary as a practitioner and then as a skilled worker who demonstrates expertise in the task. Based on his/her level of practice, he/she rates himself or herself by checking (/)the appropriate column which is described as follows:

- (1) I have started to do the task but with assistance
- (2) I can do the task well
- (3) I am confident to do the task and can assist others to do it

E. Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection commenced upon securing approval from the Research Council vi endorsement from the University Research Center. The research tool was adapted from the ECCD standards and Guidelines mandated in Republic Act 10410 or the Early Years Act. The research instrument was distributed to those who agreed to participate in this research. Additionally, permission for questionnaire

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distribution, retrieval, and interviews was sought from the Office of the Municipal Mayor of Bayombong, who is concurrently the OIC of MSWD.

F. Treatment of Data

Descriptive statistics were employed to analyze the demographic profile of the respondents. Quantitative measures, including frequency counts and percentages, were used to determine the number of Child Development Workers (CDWs) who require pedagogical support and those who are already skilled. The analysis also identified the respondents who can perform tasks effectively, as well as those who need additional support or assistance..

Ethical Considerations

This research was submitted to the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) for review and approval. SMUREB has the following address and contact information:

Email:	reb@smu.edu.ph
Mobile Number:	091771053041
Office Address:	2F Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU main Campus, Ponce St., Don Mariano Marcos, 3700 Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines

To uphold ethical standards throughout this research endeavor, the researchers adhered strictly to the following principles:

- a. *Conflict of Interest:* The researchers maintained a singular focus on the intended purpose of the study, which is primarily for educational purposes, and did not extend beyond it.
- b. *Confidentiality and Data Protection:* Ensuring the privacy of respondents and safeguarding the confidentiality of data is paramount. Therefore, the researchers refrained from disclosing the identities of respondents at any stage of the research. Instead, anonymized codes were utilized. The data collected was utilized exclusively for the research study and was securely disposed of upon completion. Both paper-based and electronic data were securely stored, with access restricted solely to the researchers.
- c. *Management of Vulnerability:* Respondents were not exposed to any form of harm in order to participate in the research survey. Participation was entirely voluntary, and respondents retained the right to withdraw from the study at any point. Participants who experienced discomfort during the research process were provided with the necessary assistance.
- d. *Informed Consent:* Prior to the commencement of the study, informed consent was thoroughly explained to the respondents and subsequently administered to them.
- e. *Risks of the Study:* Participation in the study carried no inherent risks for the participants.

f. *Benefits of the Study:* Engagement in the study will contribute to the enhancement of the child development workers of Bayombong. The findings will serve as a basis to formulate policies and initiatives concerning the child development workers, thereby benefiting both the current community and future generations.

g. *Terms of Reference:* The American Psychological Association (APA) 7th edition guidelines will be adhered to for citation and proper sourcing of materials utilized in the study. Upon completion, the study will undergo plagiarism scanning.

Results and Discussions

I. Profile of Child Development Workers

A. Age

The age distribution of the respondents in this study reveals that the majority fall within the middle-aged group (35–55 years old), comprising thirteen (13) child development workers, or 72% of the total respondents. Meanwhile, three (3) respondents, or 16.66%, belong to the senior age group, and two (2), or 11.11%, fall within the young age group. This information is summarized in the table below.

Table 1. Respondents' Profile Based on Age

Age Group	Frequency	Percent
20-25	1	5.55
26-30	1	5.55
31-35	1	5.55
36-40	2	11.11
41-45	6	33.33
46-50	2	11.11
51-55	2	11.11
56-60	2	11.11
61-65	1	5.55
TOTAL	18	100

B. Gender

The data indicate that the majority of the respondents are female, accounting for seventeen (17) individuals or 94.44% of the total. Only one (1) respondent, or 5.56%, is male. This information is presented in the table below.

Table 2. Respondents' Profile Based on Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	1	5.2
Female	17	94.7
TOTAL	18	100

Table 2 shows that there are 17 female child development workers and there is only 1 male.

C. Number of Years teaching in the Daycare center

The data, as shown in the table below, reveal that eleven (11) respondents, or 61.11%, have 1–10 years of service as daycare workers. Six (6) respondents, or 33.33%, have been in service for 11–20 years, while one (1) respondent has 36–40 years of experience in the field.

Table 3. Respondents' Profile in Terms of no. of years in teaching day care pupils

No. of Years	Frequency	Percent
1-5	6	33.33
6-10	5	27.77
11-15	4	22.22
16-20	2	11.11
36-40	1	5.55
TOTAL	18	100

Table 3 indicates tha

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D. In-Service Trainings Attended

The table below presents the number of training seminars attended by the respondents over the past three years. All eighteen (18) respondents, or 100%, have attended at least one seminar, typically conducted before the start of classes. Ten (10) respondents, or 55.55%, have participated in two seminars focused on early childhood education, while four (4) have attended three seminars. For seminars held outside the province, only one representative is usually sent, which explains why only two (2) respondents have attended four to five seminars.

Table 4. Respondents' Profile in Terms of In-Service Training Attended in day care

No. of In-service Training attended	Frequency
1	18
2	10
3	4
4	2
5	2

II. Number of CDWs who are skilled and who need pedagogical support in the different domains

A. DOMAIN: Child Growth, Development, and Learning

Table 5: Respondent's responses in Domain A

DOMAIN: Child Growth, Development and Learning				
TASKS	I have started to do the task but with assistance	I can do the task well	I am confident to do the task and can assist others to do it	N
1. Explain the different developmental domains	5 (27.77%)	6 (33.33%)	7 (38.88%)	18
2. Describe the different developmental characteristics of a child	5 (27.77%)	6 (33.33%)	7 (38.88%)	18
3. Recognize that a child develops along a continuum that is unique to each individual	3 (16.66%)	8 (44.44%)	7 (38.88%)	18
4. Articulate that development is continuous and generally sequential	3 (16.66%)	9 (50%)	6 (33.33%)	18
5. Apply knowledge of child development and learning in determining children at risk for delays	3 (16.66%)	7 (38.88%)	8 (44.44%)	18
6. Employ principles of child growth and development	2 (11.11%)	11 (61.11%)	5 (27.77%)	18
7. Use play as a vehicle for learning the physical, cognitive, language, socio-emotional, creative, and aesthetic domains	2 (11.11%)	9 (50%)	7 (38.88%)	18
8. Respond to the needs of a child based on his/her developmental characteristics	2 (11.11%)	10 (55.55%)	6 (33.33%)	18
10. Demonstrate understanding of the child's background	2 (11.11%)	13 (72.22%)	6 (33.33%)	18
11. Accept each child as a unique individual, including his/her diverse linguistic, cultural, and social backgrounds	1 (5.55%)	7 (38.88%)	10 (55.55%)	18

The table highlights the varying levels of confidence among respondents in performing tasks related to Domain A, which focuses on understanding child development. The findings suggest that the majority of respondents demonstrate high confidence in performing certain tasks. Specifically, they are most confident in explaining the different developmental domains (7 respondents), describing the various developmental characteristics of the child (7 respondents), applying knowledge of child development to identify children at risk for developmental delays (8 respondents), and accepting each child

as a unique individual, acknowledging their diverse linguistic, cultural, and social backgrounds (10 respondents).

These findings align with literature suggesting that early childhood educators' knowledge of child development is crucial for promoting healthy development and addressing developmental delays (Berk, 2013). The ability to recognize and respect the unique backgrounds and experiences of each child also plays a significant role in creating inclusive learning environments (Gonzalez-Mena, 2014).

Furthermore, a number of respondents express confidence in recognizing that child development occurs along a continuum unique to each individual (8 respondents), articulating that development is continuous and generally sequential (9 respondents), employing principles of child growth and development (11 respondents), and utilizing play as a tool for learning across various domains (physical, cognitive, language, socio-emotional, creative, and aesthetic) (9 respondents). The use of play in development is well-supported in research, which emphasizes its role in fostering holistic development (Pica, 2017). Additionally, the ability to respond to a child's individual needs based on developmental characteristics and background demonstrates an understanding of the dynamic nature of development (Santrock, 2015).

However, the findings also suggest that some respondents require additional support in performing tasks under Domain A. In particular, they struggle with explaining the different developmental domains (5 respondents) and describing the developmental characteristics of children (5 respondents). This highlights the need for continued professional development in these areas, as studies indicate that a deep understanding of developmental domains and characteristics is essential for making informed decisions in early childhood education (Pianta, 2012).

B. DOMAIN: Health, safety, Nutrition and Well-being

Table 6. Respondent's responses in Domain B

DOMAIN: Health, safety, Nutrition and Well-being				
TASKS	I have started to do the task but with assistance	I can do the task well	I am confident to do the task and can assist others to do it	N
1. Organize an up-to-date health record and history of each child	2 (11.11%)	11 (61.111%)	5 (27.77%)	18

2. Uses nutritional status, log of injuries/ illness, and medication (if ever) as intervention/s	2 (11.11%)	11 (61.111%)	5 (27.77%)	18
3. Practices a daily health check	3 (16.66%)	9 (50%)	6 (33.33%)	18
4. Keeps a pleasant, clean, and safe environment	2 (11.11%)	7 (38.88%)	9 (50%)	18
5. Show alertness to refer infants and toddlers for other health and nutrition services such as vaccines, oral health care, and micronutrient Supplementation	3 (16.66%)	9 (50%)	6 (33.33%)	18
6. Demonstrate the know-how of basic and first aid as well as preparedness in case of disaster/any emergency	6 (33.33%)	9 (50%)	3 (16.66%)	18
7. Use a first aid kit and contact the appropriate person in case of an emergency	3 (16.66%)	6 (33.33%)	9 (50%)	18
8. Show interest and safety of 0 to 4-year-old children in engaging them in various indoor/outdoor activities	1 (5.55%)	11 (61.111%)	7 (38.88%)	18
9. Implement policies and regulations regarding health and safety	1 (5.55%)	10 (55.55%)	7 (38.88%)	18
10. Demonstrate healthy and proper eating habits	1 (5.55%)	10 (55.55%)	7 (38.88%)	18
11. Demonstrate calmness in any circumstances so as not to cause panic and insecurity among 0 to 4-year-old children	1 (5.55%)	10 (55.55%)	7 (38.88%)	18

For Domain B, the table indicates a high level of confidence among respondents in performing tasks related to child health and safety. The majority of respondents excel in tasks such as organizing an up-to-date health record and history for each child (11), using nutritional status, logs of injuries/illnesses, and medication as interventions (11 respondents), practicing daily health checks (9 respondents), showing alertness in referring infants and toddlers for additional health and nutrition services such as vaccines, oral health care, and micronutrient supplementation (9 respondents), demonstrating basic first aid knowledge and preparedness for emergencies or disasters(9 respondents), engaging 0 to 4-year-old children in a variety of indoor and outdoor activities while ensuring their safety(11 respondents), implementing health and safety policies and regulations (10 respondents), demonstrating healthy eating habits, and maintaining calmness in stressful situations to avoid causing panic or insecurity among young children (10 respondents).

These findings align with research highlighting the essential role of early childhood educators in promoting the health, safety, and well-being of young children. The ability to manage and document children's health records is fundamental to providing effective care (Vanderbilt University, 2016). Similarly, being alert to the health needs of children and demonstrating first aid preparedness is critical for responding to health emergencies (Baker & Hoelscher, 2013). The importance of providing a safe and clean environment is supported by studies showing that a safe setting is crucial for both physical and emotional

child development (Chafel & Turturro, 2002). Additionally, the respondents' ability to maintain calmness in emergencies and show attentiveness to child safety is in line with studies emphasizing the role of early childhood educators in maintaining emotional security and creating a safe environment (Zins, Weissberg, Wang, & Walberg, 2004).

However, some respondents require additional assistance in tasks such as demonstrating first aid and emergency preparedness (6), practicing daily health checks (3 respondents), referring infants and toddlers for health and nutrition services (3 respondents), and using a first aid kit and contacting the appropriate emergency personnel (3 respondents). This indicates a gap in training or confidence in handling emergency situations, which can be addressed through targeted professional development (Harrison & Trotman, 2011).

C. DOMAIN: Curriculum

Table 7. Respondent's responses in Domain C

DOMAIN: Curriculum				
TASKS	I have started to do the task but with assistance	I can do the task well	I am confident to do the task and can assist others to do it	N
1. Explain essential concepts, content areas, or domains in the early childhood curriculum	4 (22.22%)	12 (66.66%)	2 (11.1%)	18
2. Show readiness in implementing the intended curriculum, which is age-appropriate, informal, and play-based.	4 (22.22%)	11 (61.11%)	3 (16.66%)	18
3. Set goals and outcomes for individual children, including children with special needs, using their developmental level	4 (22.22%)	11 (61.11%)	3 (16.66%)	18
4. Define objectives and developmentally appropriate strategies for individual children, including children with special needs, using their developmental level	4 (22.22%)	11 (61.11%)	3 (16.66%)	18
5. Plan and implement an integrated curriculum that focuses on children's development and interests, using their language, home experiences, and cultural values	4 (22.22%)	10 (55.55%)	4 (22.22%)	18
6. Implement the intended curriculum for infants, toddlers, and pre-K learners in one's locality/community localization/ contextualization	5 (27.77%)	11 (61.11%)	2 (11.1%)	18

7. Adapt/modify the calendar of activities to meet the needs of each child	4 (22.22%)	10 (55.55%)	4 (22.22%)	18
8. Utilize biased-free (gender, culture, religion, etc.) materials, stories, and experiences in all domains/content	3 (16.66%)	12 (66.66%)	3 (16.66%)	18
9. Apply holistic mode of interactive and hands-on/play-based activities with support from parents and community	2 (11.11%)	12 (66.66%)	4 (22.22%)	18
10. Provide ample time for manipulation and exploration of materials	3 (16.66%)	13 72.22%	2 (11.1%)	18
11. Show consistently positive attitudes and model behavior expected of children rather than just telling or touching his/her hands, clapping, performing the actions, etc.	1 (5.55%)	10 (55.55%)	7 (38.88%)	18
12. Design activities that show interconnectedness by giving opportunities for the children to create, discover, and act out with self-confidence	3 (16.66%)	7 (38.88%)	8 (44.44%)	18

The research findings indicate a strong foundation in core early childhood curriculum implementation among the majority of respondents, while also highlighting specific areas needing further support. A significant number demonstrated competence in fundamental practices, such as providing ample time for material exploration (13 respondents), a cornerstone of constructivist learning (Piaget, 1952), and effectively explaining curriculum concepts (12), reflecting strong content knowledge. The commitment to inclusive practices was evident, with many respondents utilizing bias-free materials (12), crucial for fostering equitable learning environments (Gay, 2010). Furthermore, the application of holistic, play-based activities with parental and community support (12 respondents) underscored the recognition of children's multifaceted development and the importance of collaborative partnerships (Epstein, 2010). Respondents also showed readiness in implementing age-appropriate, informal, and play-based curricula (11) and in setting individualized goals for children, including those with special needs (10 respondents), aligned with principles of developmentally appropriate practice and inclusive education (Bredekamp & Copple, 2009). However, a need for assistance emerged in curriculum localization (5 respondents) and defining individualized objectives and strategies (4 respondents), suggesting a gap in adapting curricula to specific community contexts and individual needs. Notably, a group of respondents (8) exhibited advanced skills, demonstrating confidence in designing interconnected activities that foster creativity, discovery, and self-confidence. This ability to facilitate deep learning experiences and model positive behaviors, rather than relying on direct instruction, reflects a sophisticated understanding of child development and effective pedagogy (Bandura, 1977).

However, several respondents identified specific areas within the **Curriculum and Instruction** domain where they require further professional development. Notably, four (4) respondents expressed the need for improvement in explaining essential concepts, content areas, or domains in the early childhood curriculum. Similarly, four (4) respondents indicated the need to enhance their readiness in implementing an intended curriculum that is age-appropriate, informal, and play-based. Another four (4) highlighted the need for support in setting goals and outcomes for individual children, including those with special needs. In addition, five (5) respondents reported needing assistance in planning and implementing an integrated curriculum that aligns with children's developmental needs and interests, while incorporating their language, home experiences, and cultural values. Three (3) respondents noted the need to improve in adapting or modifying the calendar of activities to meet the unique needs of each child. The same number identified a need for further development in designing activities that show interconnectedness and promote opportunities for children to create, discover, and act with self-confidence. Furthermore, two (2) respondents indicated the need to strengthen their ability to apply a holistic approach through interactive, hands-on, and play-based activities, with the support of parents and the community. Finally, three (3) respondents expressed the need to provide more ample time for children's manipulation and exploration of learning materials. These findings suggest targeted areas for future training and capacity-building initiatives to support the professional growth of child development workers in delivering a high-quality, child-centered curriculum.

D. DOMAIN: The Learning Environment and Experiences

Table 8. Respondent's responses in Domain D

DOMAIN: The Learning Environment and Experiences				
TASKS	I have started to do the task but with assistance	I can do the task well	I am confident to do the task and can assist others to do it	N
1. Provide space for physical movements, like walking, tiptoeing, jumping, dancing and other play-based activities and -areas of interests	1 (5.55%)	14 (77.77%)	3 (16.66%)	18
2. Design a responsive, inclusive, and gender-fair environment and make use of community and Indigenous resources where infants /toddlers / pre-K learners initiate and extend learning through play	4 (22.22%)	10 (55.55%)	4 (22.22%)	18
3. Create a learning environment for children that is clean, safe comfortable, and conducive to developmental activities (e.g. activity/interest areas)	1 (5.55%)	11 (61.11%)	7 (38.88%)	18

4. Provide ample time for manipulation/ hands-on and exploration of materials with support from parents (as needed)	2 (11.11%)	9 (50%)	7 (38.88%)	18
5. Carry out activities that will provide opportunities for children to practice self-help skills (e.g. washing hands, toileting, eating, putting on socks, etc.)	1 (5.55%)	12 (66.66%)	5 (27.77%)	18
6. Utilize learning centers/interest areas to encourage learning, development of values (e.g. self-worth, self-confidence, independence, good manners, and right conduct), and communication (either orally or through gestures)	4 (22.22%)	9 (50%)	5 (27.77%)	18
7. Implement activities efficiently and with flexibility according to needs...				
- indoor/outdoor activities	3 (16.66%)	10 (55.55%)	5 (27.77%)	18
- quieting time/rest/sleep	1 (5.55%)	12 (66.66%)	5 (27.77%)	18
- mealtime/breast/milk feeding	(16.66%)3	9 (50%)	6 (33.33%)	18
- storytelling time, etc.	2 (11.11%)	10 (55.55%)	6 (33.33%)	18

The research findings reveal a generally positive trend in respondents' ability to create developmentally appropriate learning environments for young children. A significant portion demonstrated proficiency in facilitating physical movement activities (15 respondents), which aligns with the understanding that gross motor skills are foundational in early childhood development (Gallahue & Donnelly, 2003). Similarly, many respondents successfully implemented activities promoting self-help skills (12 respondents), reflecting the importance of fostering independence and practical life skills (Dunst et al., 2000). Notably, a subset of respondents (7) exhibited confidence and expertise in establishing clean, safe, and stimulating learning environments, further emphasizing the significance of a conducive physical space for children's growth and exploration. This aligns with the principles of creating a "prepared environment" as advocated by Montessori (1967). Moreover, these 7 respondents also felt confident in providing ample time for manipulation/hands-on materials with parental support. However, areas requiring further development were also identified. Some respondents (5) expressed a need for assistance in designing responsive, inclusive, and gender-fair environments, particularly when utilizing community and Indigenous resources to foster child-initiated play. This underscores the importance of culturally responsive pedagogy and the integration of local knowledge into early childhood programs (Gay, 2010). Additionally, a few respondents (4) sought guidance in effectively utilizing learning centers to promote values development and communication skills. This highlights the ongoing need for professional development that emphasizes the holistic development of young children, encompassing social, emotional, and communicative domains alongside cognitive and physical growth.

E. Domain: Assessment and Reporting

Table 9. Respondent's responses in Domain E

DOMAIN: Assessment and Reporting				
TASKS	I have started to do the task but with assistance	I can do the task well	I am confident to do the task and can assist others to do it	N
1. Shows mastery in conducting the Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD) Checklist and other assessment tools in determining the child's development	4 (22.22%)	11 (61.11%)	3 (16.66%)	18
2. Observe the children daily in a variety of situations using different techniques (i.e. child health records, running/physical motor records, samples of the child's work, etc.)	2 (11.11%)	12 (66.66%)	4 (22.22%)	18
3. Evaluate a child's progress or lack thereof using the assessment results	2 (11.11%)	13	3 (16.66%)	18
4. Interpret and use all data of assessment results maximally for decision-making and providing appropriate intervention	4 (22.22%)	10 (55.55%)	4 (22.22%)	18
5. Identify if a child is developing adequately	2 (11.11%)	12 (66.66%)	4 (22.22%)	18
6. Describe if a child is at risk for developmental delay	6 (33.33%)	9 (50%)	3 (16.66%)	18
7. Distinguish if a child is gifted (gifted if the mental age is above the chronological age or has advanced developmental milestones)	5 (27.77%)	11 (61.11%)	2 (11.11%)	18
8. Implement appropriate interventions to enhance growth and development and help address developmental delays	6 (33.33%)	10 (55.55%)	2 (11.11%)	18
9. Seek expert's advice about other kinds of tests/referrals as needed	6 (33.33%)	8	4 (22.22%)	18
10. Demonstrate sensitivity and objectivity as possible in giving the true picture of the growth and development of the whole child I am responsible for assessment without discrimination and judgment	2 (11.11%)	10 (55.55%)	6 (33.33%)	18

11. Produce a portfolio of every child that contains relevant assessment data	1 (5.55%)	11 (61.11%)	6 (33.33%)	18
12. Recognize and make referrals for suspected developmental delays	4 (22.22%)	12 (66.66%)	2 (11.11%)	18
13. Report the information about the child's progress and developmental milestones to families and service providers	4 (22.22%)	9 (50%)	5 (27.77%)	18

The research findings indicate that respondents generally demonstrate strong competencies in early childhood assessment and reporting, while also pinpointing areas requiring further support. A significant number of respondents (13) reported proficiency in evaluating children's progress using assessment results, a crucial skill for informing instructional decisions and tailoring interventions. This aligns with the principles of formative assessment, which emphasizes ongoing monitoring to guide learning (Black & Wiliam, 1998). Furthermore, many respondents (12) effectively utilize daily observations and various assessment techniques, reflecting a commitment to comprehensive and authentic assessment practices. The ability to conduct the ECCD Checklist and other assessment tools (11), as well as to identify giftedness and recognize developmental delays (12), suggests a solid understanding of child development and assessment instruments. This is vital for early identification and intervention, which can significantly impact children's long-term outcomes (Shonkoff & Phillips, 2000). However, a notable area of concern emerged: a subset of respondents (6) expressed a need for assistance in describing if a child is at risk for developmental delay and implementing appropriate interventions, including seeking expert advice for further testing or referrals. This highlights the importance of providing educators with specialized training in identifying and addressing developmental risks, ensuring timely and effective support for children who may need it. This need to enhance intervention strategies is also supported by the fact that 6 respondents also expressed a need for help in implementing appropriate interventions.

F. Domain: Family Involvement and Community Linkages

Table 10. Respondent's responses in Domain F

DOMAIN: Family Involvement and Community Linkages				
TASKS	I have started to do the task but with assistance	I can do the task well	I am confident to do the task and can assist	N

			others to do it	
1. Recognize and respect each child's family as the first teacher	---	9 (50%)	9 (50%)	18
2. Exhibit a positive relationship with families and maintains open communication	---	11 (61.11%)	7 (38.88%)	18
3. Involve families and communities in various activities	---	10 (55.55%)	8 (44.44%)	18
4. Partner with parents in monitoring the developmental milestones of the child and implementing interventions	3 (16.66%)	11 (61.11%)	4 (22.22%)	18
5. Demonstrate awareness of the community resources and their services to be accessed	3 (16.66%)	11 (61.11%)	4 (22.22%)	18
6. Make use of the community facilities, especially the parks, playground, nutrition/health, and nutrition centers as laboratories for development and care	3 (16.66%)	10 (55.55%)	5 (27.77%)	18
7. Recognize and appreciate the support of the community resources, be it human or material	---	11 (61.11%)	7 (38.88%)	18
8. Involve the community in sharing accountability for the children's development, progress, and welfare	4 (22.22%)	10 (55.55%)	4 (22.22%)	18
9. Advocate the involvement of parents/families and the community in protecting children from abuse and other man-made hazards	5 (27.77%)	9 (50%)	4 (22.22%)	18

The research indicates that respondents generally understand and value family involvement and community linkages in early childhood education, with some demonstrating leadership in this area. A significant number of respondents (13) reported proficiency in evaluating children's progress using assessment results, a crucial skill for informing instructional decisions and tailoring interventions. This aligns with the principles of formative assessment, which emphasizes ongoing monitoring to guide learning (Black & Wiliam, 1998). Furthermore, many respondents (12) effectively utilize daily observations and various assessment techniques, reflecting a commitment to comprehensive and authentic assessment practices. The ability to conduct the ECCD Checklist and other assessment tools (11), as well as to identify giftedness and recognize developmental delays (12), suggests a solid understanding of child development and assessment instruments. This is vital for early identification and intervention, which can significantly impact children's long-term outcomes (Shonkoff & Phillips, 2000). However, a notable area of concern emerged: a subset of respondents (6) expressed a need for assistance in describing if a child is at risk for developmental delay and implementing

appropriate interventions, including seeking expert advice for further testing or referrals. This aligns with the concept of family-centered practice, which emphasizes respecting and valuing families' knowledge and expertise (Dunst et al., 2000). However, a notable area requiring attention is the advocacy for parental and community involvement in protecting children from abuse and man-made hazards, with five respondents expressing a need for assistance. This highlights the importance of equipping educators with the skills and knowledge to address child protection issues and to effectively engage families and communities in safeguarding children's well-being. This need for advocacy training is very important because it is the responsibility of every adult to protect children.

G. Domain: Personal Growth and Professional Development

Table 11. Respondent's responses in Domain G

DOMAIN: Personal Growth and Professional Development				
TASKS	I have started to do the task but with assistance	I can do the task well	I am confident to do the task and can assist others to do it	N
Manifest personal qualities such as:	2 (11.11%)	9 (50%)	7 (38.88%)	18
1. Being sensitive to the needs, interests, and holistic development of children				
2. Being creative, innovative, and resourceful	1 (5.55%)	11 (61.11)	6 (33.33%)	18
3. Being patient, flexible, and adaptable to change	----	9 (50%)	9 (50%)	18
4. love and care for infants and toddlers	----	10 (55.55%)	8 (44.44%)	18
5. ability to sing, dance, move, and tell stories with emotions to promote communication, social, and aesthetic skills	----	11 (61.11)	7 (38.88%)	18
6. Communicate well in both oral and written using English and Filipino as well as Mother Tongue in the community center he/she serves	2 (11.11%)	8 (44.44%)	8 (44.44%)	18
7. Know by heart and abide by the professional and ethical standards related to early childhood practices	1 (5.55%)	10 (55.55%)	7 (38.88%)	18
8. Show willingness to continue learning and upgrade profession to better fulfill one's mission as (11.11%) a Child Development Teacher (CDT) or Child Development Worker (CDW)	2 (11.11%)	9 (50%)	7 (38.88%)	18

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9. Take pride in being a Child Development Teacher / Worker	2 (11.11%)	9 (50%)	7	18
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The research findings reveal a generally positive trend in respondents' personal growth and professional development, with a strong emphasis on creativity, ethical conduct, and adaptability. A significant number of respondents (11) demonstrated proficiency in creative and resourceful practices, including storytelling, singing, and dancing, which are essential for fostering communication, social, and aesthetic skills in young children. This aligns with the understanding that arts-based approaches are highly effective in early childhood education (Wright, 2012). Furthermore, these respondents exhibited a caring and loving approach towards infants and toddlers, and demonstrated adherence to professional and ethical standards, highlighting their commitment to responsible practice. A group of respondents (9) displayed confidence and leadership, expressing their ability to assist others in developing patience, flexibility, and adaptability, which are crucial qualities for navigating the dynamic nature of early childhood settings. However, a small subset of respondents (2) indicated a persistent need for assistance in several key areas. These included enhancing sensitivity to children's needs and holistic development, improving communication skills in English, Filipino, and the local Mother Tongue, demonstrating a willingness to engage in continuous learning and professional development, and cultivating a sense of pride in their role as Child Development Teachers/Workers. This highlights the importance of providing targeted professional development opportunities that address these specific needs, ensuring that all educators are equipped to effectively support children's growth and development. The need for continued professional development is vital in early childhood education because of the rapid development children undergo, and the need for educators to stay up to date on best practices.

III. What insights can be drawn from the experiences of the CDWs?

The child development workers (CDWs) of Bayombong demonstrate a strong commitment to their roles in nurturing and educating the young children entrusted to their care. Their expressed desire for continuous learning in the field of early childhood education reflects a sincere dedication to personal and professional growth. This commitment is grounded in their aspiration to better respond to the developmental needs of children and to deepen their understanding of their responsibilities as child development professionals.

While many of the respondents exhibit confidence and competence across various domains of early childhood education, the findings also indicate specific areas where further enhancement is needed. In particular, a number of CDWs would benefit from a more comprehensive understanding of child development principles and practices. This underscores the importance of offering targeted professional development opportunities

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that address these specific needs, ensuring all educators are fully equipped to support each child's holistic growth and learning.

Given the rapid pace of children's development and the evolving landscape of early childhood education, continuous professional development is not just beneficial—it is essential. The areas identified below outline the key domains where support and training are most needed:

Domain A: Child Growth, Development, and Learning

Some CDWs face challenges in clearly explaining the different developmental domains and in describing the developmental characteristics of children at various stages.

Domain B: Health, safety, Nutrition and Well-being

Professional support is needed in areas such as demonstrating first aid and emergency preparedness, conducting daily health checks, referring infants and toddlers for health and nutrition services, and correctly using first aid kits and contacting appropriate emergency personnel.

Domain C: Curriculum

Several areas of improvement were identified, including:

Explaining essential concepts and content in the early childhood curriculum

Implementing a curriculum that is age-appropriate, informal, and play-based

Planning and implementing an integrated curriculum that reflects children's development, interests, home experiences, and cultural values

Designing interconnected activities that encourage creativity, discovery, and self-expression

Applying holistic, hands-on, and interactive teaching strategies, supported by parental and community involvement

Domain D: The Learning Environment and Experiences

Some CDWs require guidance in designing responsive, inclusive, and gender-fair environments, particularly when integrating community and Indigenous resources to support child-initiated play and in maximizing the potential of learning centers to foster values development and communication.

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Domain E: Assessment and Reporting

There is a need to strengthen skills in identifying children who may be at risk for developmental delays and in implementing appropriate early interventions.

Domain F: Family Involvement and Community Linkages

CDWs expressed a need for more training in advocating for parental and community involvement, especially in efforts to protect children from abuse, neglect, and man-made hazards.

Domain G: Personal Growth and Professional Development

Enhancement is also needed in developing sensitivity to children’s needs and holistic development, improving communication skills in English, Filipino, and the local mother tongue, fostering a strong commitment to continuous learning and professional development, and cultivating a deep sense of pride and identity in their roles as Child Development Teachers/Workers.

IV. Proposed Plan of Action for the Upskilling of the CDWs of Bayombong

PROJECT TITLE	Growing Together: An Upskilling Initiative for Child Development Workers
RATIONALE	<p>Child Development Workers (CDWs) play a vital role in shaping the foundational years of children, especially in underserved communities. A recent competency assessment revealed varying levels of proficiency among the CDWs in key areas of early childhood education.</p> <p>“Growing Together” is a capacity-building initiative designed to upskill CDWs, particularly those identified as needing support, while also offering a valuable refresher for more experienced workers. This initiative recognizes that investing in CDWs is an investment in the quality of care, education, and developmental outcomes of young children.</p> <p>“Growing Together” is more than a training- it is a meaningful investment in the people who shape young lives every day. By equipping Child Development Workers with up-to-date knowledge and practical tools, we strengthen the entire ecosystem of early childhood care and education, ensuring that every child has the chance to thrive from the very start.</p>

OBJECTIVES	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen the foundational knowledge and practical skills of CDWS in early childhood education 2. Address identified competency gaps based on recent assessment results. 3. Foster a culture of continuous professional development among CDWs through mentoring. 4. Contribute to better development outcomes for children through skilled and responsive caregiving. 	
Target Participants	Identified CDWs who need upskilling/pedagogical support and mentoring	
Project Proponent	Saint Mary's University Grade School	
Collaborating Agencies	SMUGS, DSWD, BFP, RHU	
Project Plan		
DOMAIN	Identified Standards/Competencies	Training Topic/s
A Child Growth, Development, and Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • explaining the different developmental domains and describing the developmental characteristics of children 	Understanding Child Development and Milestones
B Health, safety, Nutrition and Well-being	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • demonstrating first aid and emergency preparedness, • practicing daily health checks • referring infants and toddlers for health and nutrition services , • using a first aid kit and contacting the appropriate emergency personnel 	Health, Safety and Nutrition
C Curriculum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • explaining essential concepts, content areas, or domains in the early childhood curriculum, • implementing an intended curriculum that is age- 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Curriculum Planning 2. Thematic/Integrative Approach in Early Childhood Education

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	<p>appropriate, informal, and play-based,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • planning and implementing an integrated curriculum that aligns with children's developmental needs and interests, while incorporating their language, home experiences, and cultural values, • designing activities that show interconnectedness and promote opportunities for children to create, discover, and act with self-confidence, • apply a holistic approach through interactive, hands-on, and play-based activities, with the support of parents and the community 	<p>3. Play-based Curriculum</p>
<p>D The Learning and Environment Experiences</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • designing responsive, inclusive, and gender-fair environments, particularly when utilizing community and Indigenous resources to foster child-initiated play and utilizing learning centers • promote values development and communication . 	<p>Inclusive caregiving: inclusive Practices for diverse learners</p>

E Assessment and Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> describing if a child is at risk for developmental delay implementing appropriate interventions 	Supporting children with special/additional educational needs
F Family Involvement and Community Linkages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> advocacy for parental and community involvement in protecting children from abuse and man-made hazards 	Home and School Partnership
G Personal Growth and Professional Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enhancing sensitivity to children's needs and holistic development, improving communication skills in English, Filipino, and the local Mother Tongue, cultivating a sense of pride in their role as Child Development Teachers/Workers. 	
Practical Application <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrations lessons and simulations Role-playing and classroom scenarios Group discussions, experience-sharing and reflection activities 		
Expected Results <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Improved competency in Early Childhood Education practices. Increased confidence in applying inclusive and age-appropriate strategies. Enhanced quality of child engagement in community centers. Greater motivation among CDWs. Readiness for future certification programs 		
Timeline Target start: June 2025	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Seek approval of the plan 	Week 1 Week 2

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	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Planning and Finalization with the Team 3. Pre-training Orientation 4. Training Proper 5. Practical Applications 6. Post-training Assessment 7. Site Visits, and Evaluation 8. Supervision and Mentoring and 	<p>Week 3</p> <p>Week 4</p> <p>Week 5</p> <p>Week 6</p> <p>Week 7-8</p> <p>Week 10 onwards</p>
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Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion:

The assessment results reveal that, while many child development workers demonstrate baseline competence in core domains, there are critical areas requiring further development by some CDWs (5 respondents), particularly in understanding specific developmental characteristics, executing health and safety protocols, and identifying children at risk for developmental delays. These gaps underscore the urgent need for sustained, high-quality professional development to ensure child development workers are fully equipped to support the comprehensive and evolving needs of young children.

Recommendations

To effectively address the identified needs, the following actions are recommended:

1. **Implement the Strategic Upskilling Plan**
 The strategic plan of action may be rolled out, aiming at enhancing the competencies of Child Development Workers (CDWs), with a particular focus on those who require support across various domains.
2. **Invest in Continuous Professional Development**
 The Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) could invest in the ongoing professional growth of CDWs. This initiative can significantly improve the

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quality of care and learning experiences for young children—especially those at risk—promoting more equitable and positive developmental outcomes.

3. **Strengthen Collaboration Between SMU and DSWD**

Saint Mary's University (SMU) and DSWD may foster partnership to support the professionalization of CDWs who have not yet completed their bachelor's degrees, through the Expanded Tertiary Education Equivalency and Accreditation Program (ETEEAP).

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